

Introduction: Wrinkle ridges are the surface expressions of underlying faults, which develop due to compressional stresses in the crust [1-13]. Wrinkle ridges display a variety of morphologies, such as symmetric ridges, arch-style ridges, and double ridges [1, 2]. High-resolution imaging, topography, and simulation studies link these variations to different fault geometries, such as buckle folds [2], straight simple thrust faults [3, 4], conjugate thrust faults [5], fault-bend folds [6, 7], kink-type fault-propagation folds [8, 9] main thrusts with backthrusts [1, 3, 4, 10, 11, 12], and listric thrust faults [13]. Despite extensive research, there is no consensus on fault geometries since similar surface morphologies can arise from different underlying geometries [8, 13].

Wrinkle ridges often crosscut impact craters, providing valuable insights into their formation and underlying fault geometries [8, 14, 15, 16, 17]. The crosscutting relationships between wrinkle ridges and craters can provide a clearer understanding of the subsurface geometry of wrinkle ridges by revealing fault propagation patterns, such as whether the underlying fault includes a backthrust or follows a simple thrust or reverse fault geometry. We have used such interactions to understand fault structures on the Moon, and one such example is shown in Fig. 1.

Fig. 1: Craters are highlighted with yellow circles, while pink thrust fault symbols mark cross-cutting regions, with triangular teeth indicating the hanging wall direction.

Methodology: In this study, we utilized georeferenced Lunar Reconnaissance Orbiter Camera (LROC) Narrow Angle Camera (NAC) images with resolutions of ~0.5–2 m/pixel to identify crosscut impact craters [18]. Then, using ArcGIS, we mapped these craters. For topographic analysis, we used SLDEM2015 with a resolution of ~3–4 m [19].

Summary: Craters 1, 2, 3, and 4 in Fig. 1 are crosscut by the same wrinkle ridge but in opposite directions. Crater 1 is crosscut on its western side, while craters 2, 3, and 4 are crosscut on their eastern sides, suggesting opposite propagation of the same wrinkle ridge. This pattern indicates the possible presence of a backthrust fault, with the uplifted section corresponding to the antiformal region. Furthermore, the interaction between faulting and pre-existing craters provides insights into how tectonic activity contributes to crater degradation in the current tectonic setting. Overall, crosscut craters serve as important structural markers for interpreting fault propagation patterns and identifying complex fault geometries.

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